

A limit problem of the Smarandache dual function $S^{**}(n)$ ¹

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the Smarandache dual function $S^{**}(n)$ is defined as

$$S^{**}(n) = \begin{cases} \max \{2m : m \in N^*, (2m)!! \mid n\}, & 2 \mid n; \\ \max \{2m - 1 : m \in N^*, (2m - 1)!! \mid n\}, & 2 \nmid n. \end{cases}$$

The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the convergent properties of an infinity series involving $S^{**}(n)$, and give an interesting limit formula for it.

Keywords The Smarandache dual function, limit problem, elementary method.

§1. Introduction and Results

For any positive integer n , the Smarandache dual function $S^{**}(n)$ is defined as the greatest positive integer $2m - 1$ such that $(2m - 1)!!$ divide n , if n is an odd number; $S^{**}(n)$ is the greatest positive $2m$ such that $(2m)!!$ divides n , if n is an even number. From the definition of $S^{**}(n)$ we know that the first few values of $S^{**}(n)$ are: $S^{**}(1) = 1$, $S^{**}(2) = 2$, $S^{**}(3) = 3$, $S^{**}(4) = 2$, $S^{**}(5) = 1$, $S^{**}(6) = 2$, $S^{**}(7) = 1$, $S^{**}(8) = 4$, \dots . About the elementary properties of $S^{**}(n)$, some authors had studied it, and obtained many interesting results. For example, Su Gou [1] proved that for any real number $s > 1$, the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)}{n^s}$ is absolutely convergent, and

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)}{n^s} = \zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \left(1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{((2m+1)!!)^s}\right) + \zeta(s) \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{((2m)!!)^s}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

Yanting Yang [2] studied the mean value estimate of $S^{**}(n)$, and gave an interesting asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} S^{**}(n) = x \left(2e^{\frac{1}{2}} - 3 + 2e^{\frac{1}{2}} \int_0^1 e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} dy\right) + O(\ln^2 x),$$

where $e = 2.7182818284 \dots$ is a constant.

¹This work is supported by the Shaanxi Provincial Education Department Foundation 08JK433.

Yang Wang [3] also studied the mean value properties of $S^{**}(n)^2$, and prove that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} S^{**}(n)^2 = \frac{13x}{2} + O\left(\left(\frac{\ln x}{\ln \ln x}\right)^3\right).$$

In this paper, we using the elementary method to study the convergent properties of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s},$$

and give an interesting identity and limit theorem. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any real number $s > 1$, we have the identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s} = \zeta(s) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m}{((2m+1)!!)^s} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m-4}{((2m)!!)^s} \right],$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

From this Theorem we may immediately deduce the following limit formula:

Corollary. We have the limit

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (s-1) \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s} \right) = \frac{13}{2}.$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of our theorem directly. It is clear that $S^{**}(n) \ll \ln n$, so if $s > 1$, then the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s}$ is convergent absolutely, so we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s} = \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s} + \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2|n}}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s} \equiv S_1 + S_2,$$

where

$$S_1 = \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s}, \quad S_2 = \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2|n}}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s}.$$

From the definition of $S^{**}(n)$ we know that if $2 \nmid n$, we can assume that $S^{**}(n) = 2m-1$, then $(2m-1)!! \mid n$. Let $n = (2m-1)!!u$, $2m+1 \nmid u$. Note that the identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^s} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)^s} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s),$$

so from the definition of $S^{**}(n)$ we can deduce that ($s > 1$),

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_1 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{u=1, 2 \nmid u \\ 2m+1 \nmid u}}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)^2}{((2m-1)!!)^s u^s} \\
 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)^2}{((2m-1)!!)^s} \sum_{\substack{u=1, 2 \nmid u \\ 2m+1 \nmid u}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{u^s} \\
 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)^2}{((2m-1)!!)^s} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^s} - \frac{1}{(2m+1)^s} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^s} \right) \\
 &= \zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s} \right) \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)^2}{((2m-1)!!)^s} - \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)^2}{((2m+1)!!)^s} \right) \\
 &= \zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s} \right) \left(1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m+1)^2 - (2m-1)^2}{((2m+1)!!)^s} \right) \\
 &= \zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s} \right) \left(1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m}{((2m+1)!!)^s} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

For even number n , we assume that $S^{**}(n) = 2m$, then $(2m)!! \mid n$. Let $n = (2m)!!v$, $2m+2 \nmid v$. If $s > 1$, then we can deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_2 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{v=1 \\ 2m+2 \nmid v}}^{\infty} \frac{(2m)^2}{((2m)!!)^s v^s} \\
 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m)^2}{((2m)!!)^s} \sum_{\substack{v=1 \\ (2m+2) \nmid v}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{v^s} \\
 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m)^2}{((2m)!!)^s} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} - \frac{1}{(2m+2)^s} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right) \\
 &= \zeta(s) \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m)^2}{((2m)!!)^s} - \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m)^2}{((2m+2)!!)^s} \right) \\
 &= \zeta(s) \left(\frac{1}{2^{s-2}} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m+2)^2 - (2m)^2}{((2m+2)!!)^s} \right) \\
 &= \zeta(s) \left(\frac{1}{2^{s-2}} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m+4}{((2m+2)!!)^s} \right) \\
 &= 4\zeta(s) \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2m-1}{((2m)!!)^s}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)^2}{n^s} &= S_1 + S_2 \\ &= \zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \left(1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m}{((2m+1)!!)^s}\right) + 4\zeta(s) \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2m-1}{((2m)!!)^s} \\ &= \zeta(s) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m}{((2m+1)!!)^s} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m-4}{((2m)!!)^s}\right]. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of our Theorem.

Now we prove Corollary, note that

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{2} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{4m}{(2m+1)!!} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m-4}{(2m)!!} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{(2m-1)!!} - \frac{2}{(2m+1)!!}\right) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{4}{(2m-2)!!} - \frac{4}{(2m+2)!!}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} + 2 + 4 = \frac{13}{2} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (s-1)\zeta(s) = 1,$$

from Theorem we may immediately deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} &\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (s-1) \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S^{**}(n)}{n^s}\right) \\ &= \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (s-1)\zeta(s) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m}{((2m+1)!!)^s} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m-4}{((2m)!!)^s}\right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{4m}{(2m+1)!!} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{8m-4}{(2m)!!} = \frac{13}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Corollary.

References

- [1] Gou Su, On the Smarandache dual function, *Pure and Applied Mathematics*, **24**(2008), No. 1, 17-20.
- [2] Yang Yanting, On the mean value of a number theoretic function, *Journal of Natural Science of Heilongjiang University*, **25**(2008), No. 3, 340-342.
- [3] Wang Yang, On the quadratic mean value of the Smarandache dual function $S^{**}(n)$, *Research on Number Theory and Smarandache Notions*, Hexis, 2009, 109-115.
- [4] Zhang Wenpeng, *The elementary number theory* (in Chinese), Shaanxi Normal University Press, Xi'an, 2007.
- [5] Li Jianguhua and Guo Yanchun, *Research on Smarandache Unsolved Problems* (in Chinese), High American Press, 2009.